

A SORTING LINE
FOR SEPARATING
WOOD WASTE
INTO USABLE
FRACTIONS FOR
NEW WOOD-BASED
PANELS

PROJECT INNOVATION
FACTSHEET

Contributing to the EU's circular bioeconomy, reintegrating post-consumer fibreboard into production helps optimise wood use, extend product lifecycles, stores carbon and reduce dependence on virgin wood.

PROCESS

The EcoReFibre multi-stage sorting line enables efficient industrial scale sorting of mixed wood waste. It separates post-consumer fibreboard and solid wood into high-quality fractions suitable for new wood-based panels, with focus on fibreboard production.

ACHIEVEMENTS

- Processed more than 100 tonnes of wood waste, confirming industrial relevance.
- Recovered high purity fractions: 95% purity for solid wood (single stage) and 97% purity for fibreboard (two stages).
- Converted sorted solid wood, fibreboard, and mixed fractions into secondary raw material validating new recycling pathways.
- Sorted material was further processed into recycled fibres and fines to produce new panels, confirming suitability for MDF, HDF, insulation board and particleboard surfaces.

NEXT STEPS

Further improvements of sorting purity to enable higher quality of panels:

- Foster better upstream classification at collection
- Improve pre-sorting stages
- Optimise Machine Learning for optical sensors

PARTNERS

DIEFFENBACHER
MOVE FORWARD. TOGETHER.

CONTACTS

DIEFFENBACHER GMBH MASCHINEN- UND ANLAGENBAU

Germany

MICHAEL RUPP

Head of Business Unit Recycling

[dieffenbacher.com](https://www.dieffenbacher.com)

michael.rupp@dieffenbacher.com

SLU SWEDISH UNIVERSITY OF AGRICULTURAL SCIENCES

Department of Forest Biomaterials and Technology - Division of Wood Science and Technology | Uppsala, Sweden

Stergios Adamopoulos

Professor, Wood Science

stergios.adamopoulos@slu.se

[slu.se](https://www.slu.se)

[More information:](#)

[EcoReFibre on LinkedIn](#)

[.ecorefibre.eu](https://www.ecorefibre.eu)

This document reflects the authors' views only and neither the Agency nor the Commission are responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.

Funded by
the European Union

Photo credits: Dieffenbacher, InnovaWood.
Layout: Fovéa création.